

Multimodal Data Collection System for UAV-based Precision Agriculture Applications

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Abstract—Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) consist of emerging technologies that have the potential to be used gradually in various sectors providing a wide range of applications. In agricultural tasks, the UAV-based solutions are supplanting the labor and time-intensive traditional crop management practices. In this direction, this work proposes an automated framework for efficient data collection in crops employing autonomous path planning operational modes. The first method assures an optimal and collision-free path route for scanning the under examination area. The collected data from the oversight perspective are used for orthomosaic creation and subsequently, vegetation indices are extracted to assess the health levels of crops. The second operational mode is considered as an inspection extension for further on-site enriched information collection, performing fixed radius cycles around the central points of interest. A real-world weed detection application is performed verifying the acquired information using both operational modes. The weed detection performance has been evaluated utilizing a well-known Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), named Feature Pyramid Network (FPN), providing sufficient results in terms of Intersection over Union (IoU).

Index Terms—Path planning, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), Data gathering, Plant Inspection, Weed Detection, Precision Agriculture

I. INTRODUCTION

Remote sensing holds a key role in Precision Agriculture (PA) and Smart Farming (SM) serving as the core tool for monitoring cultivated fields [1]. The UAVs' inherent attributes of agility [2], adaptability [3], non-destructive data acquisition [4], their Internet of things (IoT) enabling nature [5], as well as their ultra-high spatial resolution of acquired images [6], compose them the preferred solution over their competitors. Satellite imagery provides data for large areas but with low spatial resolution and manned aircraft can cover large areas quickly but they are expensive alternatives. Ground systems

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Fig. 1: Holistic Path Planning Scheme for Precision Agriculture Applications.

are best suitable for close-up inspections but in a destructive manner, while also they cannot cover large areas. Thus, UAVs can be virtually assumed to be depicted on the switching spot between spatial resolution and data acquisition simplicity, creating an ever-increasing demand for UAV-related applications in the PA domain. Different sensors can be placed on UAVs, resulting in various sensory data that can mainly range between [7]: a) RGB imaging (Red, Green, and Blue wavebands); b) Multispectral imaging (several wavebands in visible and near-infrared range); c) Hyperspectral (hundreds to thousands of wavebands in visible and near-infrared regions); d) Thermal infrared imaging, and; e) Light detection and ranging (LiDAR) sensory data.

UAV technologies have been applied in a wide range of PA applications such as weed detection [8], semantic segmentation [9], [10], classification procedures [11], vegetation health monitoring [12], diseases detection [13], plant stress detection [14], crops spraying [15] and yield estimation [16]. Extensive taxonomy studies have been presented in the literature for UAV-based applications in PA regarding the type of UAVs, the equipped sensors, health indexes, and evaluation tasks [14], [17], [18]. Weed mapping is one of the most popular applications in PA aiming to identify non-desirable plants that cause losses to crop yields during their growth, as well as at harvesting. Therefore, accurate weed mapping leads to the reduction of herbicide usage preventing also the evolution of

herbicide-resistant weeds.

More often than not, different types of UAV missions are needed to cover specific PA needs [19]. The most common type of UAV mission includes a uniform mapping over an area of interest. Although several research works provide this kind of capability, they do not offer the capability of handling obstacles and no-fly-zones [20], [21]. Additionally, several close-up inspections are usually needed to verify and examine detections and intuitions with higher granularity. Usually, these inspections are needed at different stages of growth to constantly assess problematic areas and are executed by either non-UAV (employing specialized farmers and agronomists to be on the field) or manually controlled UAV missions.

Although there are UAV-based solutions that provide efficient approaches in drainage pipe mapping [22], irrigation management [23] and yield estimation [16], do not foresee path planning development for mapping and intensive targeted data collections actions. Individual practicability features should also be included towards unlocking the utilization of existing UAVs and enhancing adopt-ability from farmers and agronomists. It is of great importance to minimize human intervention during flight missions and maximize human co-operation capabilities at the same time, serving as an integral tool for a wide range of PA applications.

To tackle the aforementioned challenges, a holistic two-mode path planning solution is proposed that is capable of providing an automated way for data acquisition in agriculture applications. At a glance, the contributions of the developed system, which is outlined in Figure 1, are:

- A low-cost, yet automated, UAV-based solution for data acquisition in PA applications. Two operational modes emerge **a)** A path planning algorithm is responsible for producing the optimal route complete coverage of a given area of interest, while, at the same time, respecting no-fly zones. Subsequently, image data are processed by a ground control station and health indices can be extracted to assess the biomass levels of crops. **b)** A circular-like inspection around points of interest in the field is performed in lower altitudes to collect high-quality images providing enriched information.
- Custom android application to enable the intercommunication between UAV and ground control station, enabling the direct incorporation with existing, commercial UAVs.
- A real-world weed detection application is performed on a wheat and cotton field. The data have been acquired by the proposed PA path planning approach, using both operational modes. The quality of the gathered data is being verified by evaluating with a well-known Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), more specifically Feature Pyramid Network (FPN), in terms of Intersection over Union (IoU) providing sufficient results.

The material of this paper is organized as follows: Section II and Section III presents the UAV-based data collection system describing the path planning operational modes and the developed user-friendly interface, respectively. In Section IV the verification of the automated UAV-based data collection framework is performed, while also a real-world weed detec-

tion problem is presented. Finally, Section V summarizes the main innovations and functionalities of the proposed system.

II. UAV-BASED DATA COLLECTION SYSTEM

To cover a continuous area, it is essential to deploy a method capable of providing safe and efficient paths, while ensuring high-percentage coverage of the agricultural field. To deal with robot-related challenges faced in real-world scenarios, one should follow an end-to-end Coverage Path Planning (CPP) technique. CPP is the determination of a collision-free path that the robot must follow to pass through all the points of an area or Region Of Interest (ROI). A comprehensive review of CPP methods including their advances in many field applications is depicted in [24].

A. STC-based Coverage Path Planning PA Module

In this work, in terms of a CPP method, we utilized the Spanning Tree Coverage (STC) algorithm [25], [26]. This algorithm deploys an off-line CPP algorithm while knowing in advance any related information about the environment. The main steps of the aforementioned methodology are outlined in Figure 2.

For ease of understanding, it is assumed that the agricultural field is constrained within a rectangle in Cartesian coordinates (x, y) . As a first step, the proposed algorithm discretizes the area of interest into a set of equal cells of size D based on the user-defined information¹; the finite number of the cells represents the level of spatial resolution and the sensing capabilities of the robot used. The discretized cells are then grouped into large square-shaped cells of size $2D$ each of which is either entirely blocked (black) or entirely unblocked (white) as shown in Figure 2(a). It must be noted, that the only algorithm's requirement, is that the stationary obstacle areas within the grid cannot be smaller than a $2D$ cell. As a next step, as shown in Figure 2(b), every unoccupied $2D$ cell is translated into a node and an edge is introduced following the Von Neumann neighborhood, resulting an undirected graph. For the resulting graph, a minimum spanning tree is constructed by applying any Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) methodology (e.g. Kruskal or Prim [27]) as illustrated in Figure 2(c)-(d). A path is then created by circumnavigating this tree Figure 2(e) via a clockwise direction starting from a cell of size D while traversing every D cell which lies in the MST, producing, thus, an optimal covering path as shown in Figure 2(f). This navigation route (Figure 2(f)) has the advantage of avoiding unnecessary movements of the robot which do not contribute to the process of scanning the area. A mission starts and ends in the same place with each cell being covered only once while avoiding any obstacle/no-fly-zone possible defined within the operational area. In this way, the paths created are very suitable for energy-efficient applications taking into account energy constraints such as the battery consumption of the UAV.

Having illustrated all the main features that establish a safe and efficient path, we proceed to present an "adaptive" navigation algorithm including path planning switching features

¹obstacles (x, y, z) , image overlap (%) and flight altitude (h)

Fig. 2: Main steps of the Spanning Tree Coverage algorithm.

for monitoring agricultural resources tailored to field characteristics. Algorithm 1 outlines in pseudocode the proposed navigation algorithm.

In line 1, the user-selected area of the field, hereafter mentioned as *Polygon*, is transformed from the spatial reference system WGS84 to a North-East-Down (NED) frame where the coordinates can be defined as a Cartesian Plane shape (x, y) . The reason why this transformation is needed is that *Polygon* is initially defined by the user in a set of latitude/longitude pairs while the *Overlap* between two corresponding images in adjacent flight path lines is translated in meters by introducing a *Scanning distance* parameter (line 2), as sketched in Figure 3. Therefore, the NED projection was employed to represent both input parameters using a common metric system in meters.

Having transformed the input coordinates *Polygon* to a Cartesian Plane shape, in lines 2-7 the entire field is grouped into large 2D cells and each cell is represented as a node to which an edge is assigned. These nodes-edges (V, E) form the graph G which defines the allowed movements of the UAV within the field (lines 7-9). In lines 8-9, a graph minimization methodology is applied to the previously formed graph G

Algorithm 1 STC-based Coverage Path Planning method

Require: *Polygon, Obstacles, Overlap, Altitude*

Ensure: A sequence of waypoints

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1: WGS84 to NED      ▷ project to NED
2:  $\{Overlap, Altitude\} \rightarrow Scanning\ distance$       ▷ [26]
3: for  $row, col$  to  $x, y$  do
4:    $D \rightarrow 2D\ cells \in \mathbb{R}^2$  ▷ No. of cells based on Overlap
5: end for
6: for each node  $\in$  grid do
7:    $G = (V, E)$       ▷ add edge between nodes
8: end for
9: Apply MST algorithm to  $G$       ▷  $MST \in G$ 
10: Traverse MST through  $D$  cells. Halt when starting cell is
    encountered again.
11: if flight direction is True then      ▷ graph rotation
12:   rotate  $G$  by  $\vartheta$ 
13:   go back to line 8
14: end if
15: NED to WGS84      ▷ project to WGS84
16: return Coverage path
  
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Fig. 3: Overlap between two sequential images in adjacent parallel flight path lines for one UAV in two different time-steps upon the extracted coverage path.

and the circumnavigation phase takes place. Hence, to provide an efficient path tailored to the field, G must have the most favorable -in terms of coverage- representation within the grid. To do so, in lines 10-13 a rotation technique is introduced. The key idea is the rotation of each node within the grid by an angle ϑ in a counter-clockwise direction around its center-point. Modifying the flight's direction, there might appear more favorable configurations of G inside the grid, where the number of nodes is greater. Such configurations are more likely to provide paths that achieve a higher percentage of coverage for the given field as illustrated in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Flight path direction regulated by the ϑ .

Once a path within the grid has been determined, in line 14,

the extracted points are projected back to the WGS84 system to generate a sequence of waypoints to be used in real-world scenarios. Finally, in line 15, the output of the algorithm generates a simple closed path $(Lat_1, Lon_1), (Lat_2, Lon_2), \dots, (Lat_m, Lon_m)$, where m denotes the number of waypoints.

B. Targeted High-Detail Data Acquisition Module

Based on the resulted CPP flight, a number of aerial images will be collected and processed. After the post-processing analysis, it is usual to identify some specific spots that require more detailed “on-site” inspection. This task can be also automated by using UAVs with the appropriate path planning mechanism.

From the motion planning perspective, the planning of the route for accessing a finite set of points is limited to the problem of finding the optimal path with the minimum realization cost. For the visual “on-site” inspection, we applied the Travelling Salesman algorithm [28], a renowned method for finding the shortest path within an undirected graph. More specifically, this algorithm treats the problem as an unoriented stationary graph, with the finite points being the vertices of the graph and the edges being the paths that the UAV can follow during its mission, as illustrated in Figure 5(a). It is a problem that starts and ends at a specific vertex after having visited all the other vertices of the graph, exactly once. After calculating the optimal path, the points - vertices of the graph are “transformed” into centers of circular shapes, and a set of m additional points on the perimeter of the circle are generated. These additional points are created in the 3D space given a desired altitude h , an angle $\phi \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$ and a constant radius r . This way, along with the path formed by TSP, the UAV repeatedly performs fixed radius cycles around all central points of interest as depicted in Figure 5(b). Apparently, this operation provides enriched “on-site”/local information, as images are acquired from lower altitude levels (e.g., 10 meters) and different angles. Moreover, during the execution of the mission, the user can also use the physical remote control to modify the speed and altitude of the aircraft.

Fig. 5: Visual “on-site” inspection around a point of interest

One must note that, for both path planning modes, to acquire high-resolution images, a number of parameters (namely *Overlap*, *Altitude*, *Flight Direction*, *Speed*) should be tuned accordingly.

III. AN ANDROID-BASED MIDDLEWARE APPLICATION FOR UAVS

To provide a data collection solution able to perform coverage and inspection missions for real-life use, a UAV-

based middleware application is needed to enable message interactions and real-time communication. Towards this direction, a custom and user-friendly interface based on the UAV’s handling capabilities have been developed with the use of the DJI API offering a simplified form of on-site commands as illustrated in Figure 6. Specifically, the developed android application is used as a data transceiver between the automatic navigation algorithms and the flight control system, allowing the UAV to follow the waypoints to cover or inspect an area and collect data. Note that the aforementioned android application is configured to provide i) autonomous missions and ii) dynamic display of flight data capable of integrating different types of commercial UAVs. In addition, it also acts as an on-the-field pilot, allowing the users to monitor the missions live, enabling them to take control and handle the UAV instantly, if needed.

Fig. 6: Custom-developed android application

Based on this application, the UAV during the mission automatically stores images or video footage in an embedded micro-SD card from the area covered. Note that the sampling frequency of the captured images and the UAV’s speed should be adjusted to meet the appropriate requirements of overlap and quality (noise, blurring effect). This custom android UAV-based application is open-source and publicly available² to the research community.

IV. DEMONSTRATIVE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents two real experiments where the proposed automated UAV-based data collection framework was used to acquire qualitative and quantitative data. The objectives of the experiments were to thoroughly test the proposed autonomous navigation system and collect aerial UAV footage for two different types of precision agriculture applications i) crop-field monitoring, geo-mapping, and assessment and ii) weed detection based on image processing and computer vision techniques.

A. Hardware components

For both experiments, a commercial UAV (DJI Phantom 4 Pro) equipped with a 1-inch 20-megapixel RGB sensor was used for the data acquisition. The flight path planning for crop monitoring and weed detection was done by the developed algorithms described in the subsections II-A and

²<https://github.com/CoFly-Project/waypointmission>

II-B, respectively. To manage and control the automated missions, an android smartphone device (Xiaomi Mi Max 2) was used to run the UAV control application described in subsection III. Last but not least, a portable 4G router (tp-link M7350) was used to load the maps to adjust the UAV missions based on the field characteristics. However, it should be noted that the transferring and reception of data across devices was made internet-free via a local network enabling real-time communication with minimum latency even in locations where the internet is inaccessible.

B. STC-based Coverage Path Planning PA Module: A wheat field case

This subsection consist an experimental projection of the path planning algorithm described in II-A having an ulterior motive to provide the crops' health condition from an oversight perspective. More specifically, the under examination area is a wheat field. First, the mission planner designs the shortest possible path, avoiding unnecessary movements of the UAV (II-A), the waypoints are received by the UAV via radio signal and the autonomous mission of data collection takes place (III). The low-cost device is equipped with an RGB camera capturing images at a pre-defined sampling frequency, overlap and altitude. The off-line image processing includes orthophoto generation aiming to enhance the overall visualization extracting useful information about the crop monitoring and management. Vegetation Indices (VIs) that are based on the reflective properties of vegetation in the visible light spectral range were considered as described in Table I. The overall assessment of plant health for the under investigation field, Figure 7(a), is depicted in Figure 7(b)-(e). For better visualization and immediate monitoring perception, a color scale is applied, with low values presented in red and high values in green. The results show that the selected vegetation indices can capture the crop's state in terms of plant health enabling effective monitoring for decision-making objectives.

C. Targeted High-Detail Data Acquisition Module: A weed detection application

In this subsection, an experimental evaluation is conducted in terms of a vision-based weed detection method using a deep learning model that effectively detect weeds in UAV-captured images. In this case, we utilized the agronomist-annotated CoFly-WeedDB-dataset [29], which contains a set of 201 RGB images of size 1280×720 pixels, depicting different types of weed species among crop plants. Note that the RGB images were acquired by a Phantom 4 Pro UAV while it was performing an inspection mission as described in II-B. More specifically, in this dataset, three types of weeds were identified: 1) Johnson grass; 2) Field bindweed; 3) Purslane. In Figure 8 indicative examples of the annotated dataset, for each weed class are presented. All three weed classes have been unified as *Weed* class, while the remaining area is considered as *Background*. The objective is to validate the information content of the deployed dataset and its ability to lead to robust weed detection models.

Fig. 7: The produced orthomosaic for a wheat crop and the corresponding vegetation indices.

Fig. 8: Annotated images for each type of identified weed.

The designed validation approach was focused on the semantic segmentation task. In specific, a robust deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for semantic segmentation, with novel backbone architecture, was employed as a baseline. Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) is a typical model for semantic segmentation which has reported promising results in various cases was utilized. FPN is based on the well-known scheme of encoder-decoder. In particular, the input image is firstly processed by the encoding block, which aims at progressively reducing the spatial dimensions while simultaneously increasing the depth dimension of the extracted tensor. The aforementioned process leads to an encoded image representation yet, enclosing high-level information. In the decoding stage, the inverted process takes place, where the compact image representation is gradually upsampled while

TABLE I: Vegetation indices description

RGB-based Vegetation Index Abbreviation	Visual Atmospheric Resistance Index VARI	Green Leaf Index GLI	Normalized Green Red Difference Index NGRDI	Normalized Green Blue Difference Index NGBDI
Formula	$\frac{G-B}{G+R-B}$	$\frac{2*G-R-B}{2*G+R+B}$	$\frac{G-R}{G+R}$	$\frac{G-B}{G+B}$

the channel dimension is reduced, to produce the segmented outcome that meets the initial input dimensions. The main aspect of FPN is the employment of skip connections that add the extracted feature maps from the individual encoding levels to the corresponding layers of the decoder and employ a 1×1 convolution to further fine-tune the extracted outcome. Regarding the backbone architecture employed in the encoding stage, the family of EfficientNet networks was utilized which contains state-of-the-art results in image classification tasks.

The employed dataset was randomly split into a training and testing set, following an 80% – 20% rule. The specific process was repeated 3 times, to derive different split subsets containing divergent data distributions and thus, allow to conduct of a more detailed and concrete evaluation. Regarding the training process, the FPN model was trained for 500 epochs with a batch size equal to 16 and the Adam optimization algorithm. Since the designed dataset is imbalanced, a focal loss function was utilized aiming to tackle the specific issue. For the training stage, several augmentation techniques were employed aiming to increase the amount of processed data and thus, increase the model’s efficiency. In detail, the following augmentation methods are deployed on every training image with a chance of 50%: horizontal/vertical flip, random rotation, random rescale, gaussian blurring, and random change of the image brightness. The aforementioned techniques were selected taking into consideration that processed data are UAV-acquired imagery and our aim was to simulate different capturing scenarios by the UAV camera. Finally, the patch of 256×256 pixels is randomly cropped from every image, operating as another augmentation process, and forwarded as input to the model. All experiments were conducted on a GeForce RTX 3090 GPU.

Table II presents the accuracy of the FPN pre-described model in terms of Intersection-over-Union (IoU). Specifically, it shares EfficientNetB1 as the encoder backbone, which is pretrained on the well-known dataset ImageNet. Results are reported for each one of the three data splits with the corresponding mean value.

TABLE II: Evaluation performance of FPN in terms of IoU for three different split subsets

Model	Split	Background	Weed	mIoU
FPN	1	95.45	44.58	70.01
	2	94.93	38.81	66.87
	3	96.29	42.58	69.44

Results imply that the quality of the collected data is adequate to create robust weed detection methods based on deep learning models empowering the UAV robots also as a tool for automatic visual inspection in precision farming.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an UAV-based data collection system for precision agriculture applications has been proposed. Two path planning operational modes have been presented in order to provide compact and effective solutions for a wide range of PA-related tasks from the data collection perspective. The main path planning/navigation algorithm produces an optimal and collision-free route for data gathering in monitoring-related applications. However, for more detail-demanding applications which require intensive crop inspection, such as weed detection, a second operational path planning mode is presented. More precisely, circular-like inspection takes place around points of interest to collect enriched local field information. All the UAV’s path planning capabilities are internet-free functioning on mobile devices including user-friendly on-site commands and flight data tracking that ease the utilization of UAVs. The functionality of the proposed system was tested and validated in two different types of precision agriculture applications. In both experiments, the proposed framework preserved all the desired features while at the same time the preliminary evaluation results showed that the collected dataset from the visual inspection mission can lead to robust weed detection models. These features are of paramount importance in agribusiness, as they can be utilized to design sustainable legume-supported cropping systems for monitoring, assessment, weed detection, and pest control management. As future work, we plan to extend our system to include the incorporation of several UAVs in the same mission, using a combination of offline path-planning [30] and an online adaptation [31], to reduce the execution time by several orders of magnitude.

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